

Effect of depth of submergence on bacterial blight (BB) incidence and white grub infestation in transplanted rice, 1973 wet season. Pantnagar, India.

Treatment	BB ^a disease index	White grub damage (%)
15 cm – 1 cm	5.07	1.6
5 cm – field capacity	4.15	3.3
1 cm – field capacity	1.65	11.5
36 cm total water (50% total water use)	0.87	20.4
Rainfed	0.90	17.5
CD at 5%	1.07	5.0
CV %	28.00	30.5

^aOn 0–9 All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP) scale, where 0 = no disease incidence.

in the deep and shallow submergence treatments than in the saturation and rainfed treatments. ■

Oxadiazon, a promising herbicide for dry-seeded rice in Sudan Gezira

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The semiarid Sudan Gezira has good potential for high rice production; it is rich in solar radiation and free from major pests. It has well-controlled irrigation but because of socioeconomic factors, farmers drill rice directly into dry soil and water the crop as needed until flooding commences 6 weeks after seeding. The result is severe infestation of upland weeds of the genera *Phyllanthus*, *Leucas*, *Aristolochia*, *Echinochloa*, *Solanum*, *Momordica*, *Cyperus*, *Merremia*, and *Ocimum*.

Hand weeding is tedious and costly, and herbicides have been used unsuccessfully because they have been applied without any preevaluation. The identification of effective herbicides suitable for controlling dominant weed species such as *P. niruri* and *L. urticifolia* is therefore essential.

In 1978, 11 herbicide treatments plus hand-weeded and unweeded controls were laid out in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications at the Gezira Agricultural Research Farm. The herbicides were applied at recommended rates and times. A knapsack sprayer was used to deliver about 450 liters/ha.

Effects of 11 herbicides on grain yield of the rice IR2053-206-1-3-6, and on weed density and species. Sudan Gezira, 1978.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Weeds (no./m ²)	Uncontrolled weed genera (decreasing order of density)
Oxadiazon	4.34	7.7	<i>Aristolochia</i> , <i>Solanum</i> .
X-150	4.03	13.7	<i>Aristolochia</i> , <i>Solanum</i> , <i>Merremia</i> .
Oxyfluorfen	3.43	12.6	<i>Aristolochia</i> , <i>Solanum</i> .
Pendimethalin	3.25	19.2	<i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Solanum</i> , <i>Leucas</i> , <i>Aristolochia</i> .
Bentazon ^a	2.96	20.0	<i>Solanum</i> , <i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Leucas</i> , <i>Aristolochia</i> .
Dinitramine	2.78	31.7	<i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Leucas</i> , <i>Aristolochia</i> , <i>Momordica</i> .
Thiobencarb ^a	2.46	38.7	<i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Ipomea</i> , <i>Aristolochia</i> , <i>Ocimum</i> .
Butralin	2.32	30.0	<i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Leucas</i> , <i>Aristolochia</i> .
Propanil ^a	2.26	23.2	<i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Aristolochia</i> , <i>Echinochloa</i> .
Diethatyl	2.25	27.5	<i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Solanum</i> , <i>Leucas</i> .
Piperophos-dimethametryn	2.20	11.0	<i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Aristolochia</i> , <i>Echinochloa</i> .
Handweeded (20 + 40 DE) ^b	4.67	–	–
Unweeded	1.31	40.2	<i>Phyllanthus</i> , <i>Leucas</i> , <i>Aristolochia</i> , <i>Merremia</i> , <i>Momordica</i> , <i>Ipomea</i> , <i>Ocimum</i> .
S.E. ±	0.27	3.86	

^aNow used in the Gezira. ^bDays after rice emergence.

The yields of IR2053-206-1-3-6 were 72% lower in the unweeded plots than in the hand-weeded (see table). They were significantly higher in all the herbicide treatments than in the unweeded control. Oxadiazon gave the highest yield, comparable to that in the hand-weeded treatment. It effectively controlled

most of the weed flora without being phytotoxic to the rice plant. Being a preemergence herbicide, oxadiazon is preferable in the almost fully mechanized farming system of the Gezira. X-150, oxyfluorfen, and pendimethalin also were promising. ■

Egg parasites of the yellow stem borer in West Bengal

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Natural enemies play an important role in the control of populations of the rice yellow borer *Tryporyza incertulas* (Wlk.). They should be considered for maintaining homeostasis, particularly in the wet season when chemical protection is neither economical nor feasible in low-lying areas of West Bengal. Egg parasites are important components in the faunal

composition of natural enemies. Five hymenopteran insects have been noted on yellow borer egg masses at the Chinsurah Station and identified from IBP Handbook 14 as *Tetrastichus schoenobii* Ferr., *Telenomus dignus* Gahan, *Telenomus dignoides* Nixon, *Telenomus rowani* Gahan, and *Trichogramma japonicum* Ashm. The percentage of parasitism was estimated from the emergence of parasitoids from the viable eggs of field-collected egg masses (see table).

The low parasitism in March and

Egg parasitization of the yellow stem borer at Chinsurah, West Bengal, India.

Month	Egg masses (no.)	Sterile egg masses (no.)	Parasitized egg masses (no.)	Parasitization (%)
Feb	136	24	70	62
Mar	117	25	48	52
Apr	136	34	41	40
May	44	24	14	71
Jun	45	10	12	34
Jul	36	2	16	48
Aug	26	2	17	71
Sep	35	2	21	63
Oct	137	9	70	55
Nov	164	54	98	89